

“Full Paper - EFFECT OF DRILLING PARAMETERS ON SURFACE QUALITY OF NATURAL FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES”

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Abstract

Composite materials are widely recognized for their increasing applications in the area of space, aircraft, automotive and other engineering sectors. This is due to their superior characteristics such as light weight, recyclability, low materials cost and production cost, high specific strength and modulus. Drilling operations are required to facilitate assembly of the component to get final product. A hole drilled in composite material comes up with poor surface roughness, delamination and debonding of fibers with the matrix material. The present work deals with fabrication of jute and human hair based series of composites reinforced with Epoxy resin. Experiments were conducted using the samples prepared from the samples prepared from the fabricated material to study the effect of human hair in jute fiber reinforced composites. The interfacial properties and internal structure of the fractured surfaces were analyzed using Scanning Electron Microscopy. Taguchi's L9 orthogonal design was used to optimize the drilling parameters with respect to the surface roughness of the prepared composite material. Experimental results have shown significant increase in the properties of the composite materials. It has been found that the drill point angle is most contributing factor affecting the characteristics of the drilled holes. SEM images have revealed that debonding of fibers with matrix results in decrease in the strength by 18.75% and 6.25% in Human hair and jute fiber reinforced composites respectively thus leading to the poor surface roughness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hybrid composites provide combination of material properties of those individual fibers and the reinforcement used. Jute fiber falls into the bast fiber category and is an attractive natural fiber for reinforcement in composites because of its low cost, renewable nature and low energy requirement for processing. The jute based composites may be used in everyday applications such as lampshades, suitcases, paperweights, helmets, shower and bath units. Human hair that is widely available at a low cost finds abundant usage as a fiber reinforcing material in composites. Human hair has high elasticity and a lock of 100 hairs can withstand a weight of about 12 tons [1]. Epoxy resins are being widely used in advanced composites due to their excellent adhesion to a large variety of fibers and for their high performance at elevated temperatures.

Various parts of automotive vehicle such as door panel, Headliners, bumpers, engine cover and roof covers are now manufactured using composite materials. Drilling in certain cases falls as the last few operation in schedule during the assembly of the structures. Any defect that leads to the rejection of the parts in these stages represents an expensive loss. Drilling of natural fiber reinforced composites needs less thrust force and results in less tool wear compared to drilling of conventional metallic automotive parts. The variation of volume fraction of the fibers makes the drilling process more complex, as proper feed, and speed should be given to produce a perfect hole. **Ramesh et al.** [2] indicated that the addition of jute fiber with GFRP can improve the properties and can replace glass fiber reinforced polymer composites. **Salma et al.** [3] investigated the Mechanical Properties of Jute-Coir Fiber Reinforced Hybrid Polypropylene Composites. Increasing the fiber content in polymer composites helps achieving best mechanical properties. **Vishakh et al.** [4] found that the human hair reinforced with epoxy matrix withstands a compressive load of 170KN. The advantages of adding human hair in polymers is that it resists the creep formation due to their elastic behavior. **Ashish Kumar et al.** [5] investigated the effect of hair fiber volume (3%, 5% & 8%) on compressive strength of polypropylene based composite. Better results of mechanical properties are achieved in higher content of hair fiber reinforced PP composite. **Sanjay et al.** [6] mixed the Human hair fibers into polypropylene (PP) at 3%, 5%, 10% and 15 % by weight. It was concluded that Polypropylene and hair fiber polymer reinforced composite have better flexural and impact strength and lower tensile strength than pure polypropylene composites. **Senthilnathan et al.** [7] fabricated composites with human hair, sisal and glass fiber as the reinforcement and Epoxy as the matrix. Incorporation of human hair with other fibers give better results than those of individual components. **Prabhu et al.** [8] determined that there is significant influence on the tensile, flexural, impact strength and hardness values when adding kenaf-human hair with epoxy composites. **Kishore et al.** [9] evaluated the hole quality in drilling on sisal - epoxy and sisal – polypropylene composite with considering the drill geometry, speed and feed and it was observed that the volume of fiber and type of polymer in composite also influences the surface quality. **Vinayagamorthy et al.** [10] did their research on vetiver- glass reinforced vinyl ester composite for analyzing the drilling quality. The surface roughness is highly influenced by cutting speed rather than feed and tool angle. The cutting force required to produce hole also affects the hole quality. **Ramesh et al.** [11] concluded that due to cutting force the fiber matrix debonding occurs and it damages the hole.

The statement from past researches on drilling quality analysis in natural fiber reinforced composites have more influenced on cutting parameters, fiber – matrix internal relationship, volume of fiber and cutting forces. The present work concentrates on the fabrication of composites with jute and human hair as the reinforcement and Epoxy as the matrix material and also surface roughness analysis in drilling of fabricated composites by considering speed, feed and drill point angle with three levels.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials Used

Raw material used to fabricate composites is jute and human hair as the reinforcement material and epoxy as the matrix material. The jute fiber in yarn type is collected from National Jute Board Chennai in India. Human Hair is purchased at Chennai, India. The present work concentrates on the chopped type of fiber reinforcement as 20mm by length. The Epoxy Ly - 556 and corresponding hardener HY-951 was purchased at Chennai in India. The physical properties of the raw materials used are shown in Table 1.

2.2 Composite Fabrication

Hand layup method is used to fabricate the composites in the size of 300 mm x 300 mm square plate with 5 mm thickness. Five different composites were fabricated using a constant volume fraction of 25% volume of fiber and 75% volume of resin. The composition of jute and human hair in

the 25% volume of fiber is varied as mentioned in Table 2. Composite were fabricated using the mould made of silicon rubber. The cast of each composite is cured under a load of about 50 kg for 24 hours before it is removed from the mould.

2.3 Mechanical Testing of Composites

Test Samples are prepared according to ASTM standard in vertical zigzag cutting machine. For average values three samples per composite were prepared. Experiments to find the mechanical properties such as tensile, flexural and double shear strength were found by tensile test (ASTM D638), Flexural test (ASTM D790 and Double Shear test (ASTM D5379) conducted on universal testing machine. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was used to analyze the microstructure of fractured surfaces

Fiber	Density, g/cm ³	Diameter μ m	Tensile Strength, Mpa	Young's Modulus, GPa	Elongation at Break, %	Moisture Absorption, %
Jute	1.4	160-185	400-800	10-30	1.8	12
Human Hair	1.32	17-180	400	-	216.94	-
Epoxy	1.1-1.4	-	35-100	3-6	1-6	0.1-0.4

Table 1 physical properties of raw material

Composite	25% Fiber Composition
A	25% jute + 0% human hair
B	18.75% jute + 6.25% human hair
C	12.5% jute + 12.5% human hair
D	6.25% jute + 18.75% human hair
E	0% jute + 25% human hair

Table 2 composition and designation of composites

2.4 Drilling of Composite

Drilling operation was performed in three different hybrid composites under three different machining conditions such as speed, feed and drill point angle with three levels. The taguchi experimental design involves L9 orthogonal array to organize the 4 parameters with 3 levels for analyzing the surface roughness of hole. The carbide drill bit with 10 mm diameter is used to produce holes in the samples by using Hurco vm20 CNC vertical machining center. The holes thus drilled were then tested for surface roughness in Mitutoyo 5J01 surface roughness tester. The machining parameters and their levels are described in Table 3. To determine the effect each variable, the signal-to-noise ratio needs to be calculated for each experiment. The equation used to determining the SN ratio for minimizing the performance characteristics is as follows

$$SN_i = -10 \log \left\{ \sum_{u=1}^{N_i} (y^2 \div N_i) \right\}$$

level	Speed (rpm)	Feed (mm/ min)	Drill point angle (Degree)	Composite type (Fiber composition)
	P ₁	P ₂	P ₃	P ₃
1	1000	100	90	B (18.75% jute +6.25% hair)
2	1500	200	110	C (12.5% jute +12.5% hair)
3	2000	300	130	D (6.25% jute +18.75% hair)

Table 3 Machining parameters and their levels.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical Characterization

The tensile, Flexural and Double Shear test were performed in universal testing machine. The maximum load observed at breaking point is obtained and corresponding strength values of each sample from each test were evaluated. The results show that the 25% human hair reinforced composite has obtained the higher tensile, flexural and double shear properties than other composite laminates. It is seen that while increasing human hair content in jute fiber composite the tensile, flexural and double shear strength are increased as compared to 25% jute fiber reinforced epoxy composite. And also it was observed that the tensile and flexural strength is suddenly decreased in composite D due to poor bonding between fibers and resin. Figure 2 indicates complete removal of fiber from matrix during the tests.

Composite	A	B	C	D	E
Tensile Strength (MPa)	16	18.5	20	18	23.5
Flexural Strength (MPa)	66.6	61.63	81.49	75.35	80.83

Double Shear Strength (MPa)	30	28.25	32	35.5	44.45
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Table 4 Average values of mechanical properties for each composite

3.2 Micro structural Analysis of samples using SEM

SEM analysis was conducted on the fractured tensile specimens for determining the internal bonding between fiber and matrix. SEM images of the fabricated composites revealed that the 25 % jute fiber reinforced composite achieved uniform distribution of fibers with matrix results in good bonding relationship between fiber and matrix as shown in figure 1. Polymer composite reinforced with 6.25% jute and 18.75 % human hair observed that the complete removal of fiber from matrix due to the lack of adhesion between fiber and matrix is shown in the figure 2. So proper bonding should be required to improve the strength properties of fiber reinforced composites.

Figure 1 SEM image 25% jute fiber reinforced composite after tensile test

Figure 2 SEM image 6.25% jute fibers 18.75 % human hair reinforced composite after tensile test

3.3 Surface Roughness

Drilling is performed in composites by two trials per experiment. Totally 18 holes were tested. The surface roughness (R_a) of the internal periphery of the drilled holes was determined. The SN ratio and mean values of surface roughness measured were determined by using Minitab software. Output from Minitab, the Response Table 5 & 6 for Signal to Noise Ratios and Means were obtained and it is ranked as for most contribution which affecting the process.

Surface Roughness - SN ratio				
Level	Speed (rpm)	Feed (mm/min)	Drill point angle (Degree)	Composite types
1	35.18	35.09	32.90	35.02
2	35.25	35.25	35.50	33.10
3	33.14	33.23	35.17	35.45
Delta Δ	2.11	2.01	2.60	2.35

Rank	3	4	1	2
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Table 5 Response Table for Signal to Noise Ratio

Surface Roughness - Means				
Level	Speed (rpm)	Feed (mm/min)	Drill point angle (Degree)	Composite types
1	0.01717	0.01783	0.02150	0.01783
2	0.01700	0.01717	0.01700	0.02100
3	0.02167	0.02083	0.01733	0.01700
Delta Δ	0.00467	0.00367	0.00450	0.00400
Rank	1	4	2	3

Table 6 Response Table for Means

From response table the SN ratio and the mean values observed it is found that the most contributed parameters and their levels for surface roughness is in the following order,

From SN Ratio,

- Drill point Angle at level 2 (110 degree),
- Composite type at level 3 (D),
- Speed at level 2 (1500rpm),
- Feed at level 2 (200mm/min)

From Mean,

- Speed at level 2 (1500rpm),
- Drill point Angle at level 2 (110 degree),
- Composite type at level 3 (D),
- Feed at level 2 (200mm/min)

Figure 3 Plot for SN ratios of Surface Roughness

Figure 4 Plot for Means of Surface Roughness

It is observed that the composite laminate of type D contributed the second most factor which affects the hole quality. It is due to the lack of adhesion between fiber and the matrix occurred during fabrication and strength also decreased.

4. CONCLUSION

The present work of analyzing the mechanical properties and machining parameters in jute and Human hair reinforced natural composite has yielded the following results.

Mechanical properties such as Tensile, Flexural and double shear properties increase with human hair content in jute fiber reinforced composites. The 100% jute fiber composite has lower strength than the 100% Human hair composite. SEM image shows, the bonding between 6.25% jute and 18.75% hair composite is poor and reasons for the decrease strength. Based on the SN ratio the surface roughness is mostly affected by drill point angle. There is no significant effects of feed in hole quality. The optimal parameters for surface roughness are same for both SN Ratio and Mean. From the results, it is found that the Drill point angle and Speed are the major contributing factors affecting the quality of hole. So, it should be selected carefully to reduce the defects.

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